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-
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ESCALATOR STATUS REPORT

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science & innovation
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Table of Contents

Introduction - The need for ESCALATOR	01
Building a community of practice (CoP)	02
Highlights	03
Theory of change	04
Core elements of ESCALATOR	05
Spotlight: DH-IGNITE	06
Spotlight: Digital Champions Initiative	07
Spotlight: Stakeholder map	08
An overview of the community	09
Feedback from the community	10
Next steps	11
Acknowledgements	12

Introduction

The ESCALATOR programme aims to support the development of an active community of practice in digital humanities and computational social sciences in South Africa.

The Need for ESCALATOR

Over the past decade or more, several new initiatives have been launched to enhance the uptake of digital and computational-supported research methodologies within the Humanities and Social Sciences. The need for researchers within these fields to study the impact of technology such as social media, artificial intelligence, biased computer algorithms, and more on humanity has been exacerbated in the last few years. Despite the availability of numerous opportunities to grow computational and digital research skills globally, staff and students within Humanities and Social Sciences in South Africa still need more confidence and more accessible mentors when learning and applying innovative research methodologies.

The South African Centre for Digital Language Resources (SADiLaR) identified the need to create a unifying national project that brings together researchers, students and practitioners from across the Humanities, Social Sciences, and computational research areas where learning, sharing of best practices, and co-creation of resources can take place. The ESCALATOR programme was established in December 2020 to address this need.

This report provides an overview of the approach followed to establish a new national community of practice across the 26 public universities, relevant research councils and research organisations. It summarises lessons learned and proposes a way to build on the momentum gained over the past 28 months.

A note on the COVID-19 pandemic

South Africa was in a national state of disaster due to the global COVID-19 pandemic during the design and first 16 months (out of 28) of the programme. ESCALATOR was adapted to accommodate the changing working environment, limits on travel and in-person meetings, and additional pressures on university staff and students.

Building a community of practice (CoP)

A community of practice is a group of individuals who come together around a shared interest or domain of knowledge to share ideas, solve problems, and build expertise in their area of interest. Overall, communities of practice provide a platform for individuals to deepen their knowledge and skills, to collaborate with others who share their interests, and to advance their careers and personal growth.

According to the [Community Participation Model](#) developed by the Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement (CSCCE), communities evolve in terms of interactions, goals, activities, and power balance over time. Since the establishment of ESCALATOR, our community has primarily functioned in the *transmissive (conveying/consuming) phase*, with some movement to the *transactional (contributing) phase*.

Research has shown that it can take many years to establish a healthy community of practice depending on factors such as the complexity of the subject matter, the size of the group, support and sponsorship from organisations, the geographical distribution of members, and their level of commitment.

	TRANSMISSIVE	TRANSACTIONAL	TRANSFORMATIONAL
Community Participation Model	convey/consume	contribute	collaborate
	co-create	champion	
INTERACTIONS	one-to-many	crowdsourced	cooperative
COMMUNITY MANAGEMENT GOAL	inform and inspire	obtain feedback, skills, or information	gather resources, including knowledge, to achieve a common goal
COMMUNITY ACTIVITIES	read watch listen	comment vote / like tag	discussion knowledge exchange production
POWER BALANCE	organization as expert	organization as convener	scaffolded cooperation
SLOGAN	here's something interesting	give us some feedback	how can we work together?

Center for Scientific Collaboration and Community Engagement. (2020) *The CSCCE Community Participation Model – A framework for member engagement and information flow in STEM communities.* Woodley and Pratt doi:10.5281/zenodo.3997802

Highlights

Despite the impact of COVID-19, we have reached hundreds of humanities and social sciences staff and students across the country.

Activity / Project

We created new channels for sharing news and communicating with the community

Data / Outcome

We continuously improve communication with our community and explore ways to facilitate connection.

escalator.sadilar.org

twitter.com/DHCSSza

bit.ly/DHCSSza-Slack

ESCALATOR participants were asked about their needs through surveys and conversations

Top three challenges from >200 participants...

We hosted and participated in various multi-modal awareness creation and capacity development events

>200

Virtual and/or in-person opportunities

...were offered to our community to enhance their awareness and digital and computational research skills and networks.

ESCALATOR participants are receiving training on contextualised Open Educational Resources and support with proposal development

We are providing funding, proposal development guidance, and training in developing and using Open Educational Resources to...

THEORY OF CHANGE

Core elements of ESCALATOR

The programme is built on three cornerstones to achieve the desired outcomes.

The ESCALATOR programme offers a vast array of opportunities for collaboration, learning, contributing, conversation, showcasing and more. To make the programme more comprehensible and accessible, all activities are grouped under the three core elements described here.

1 DH-IGNITE EVENTS

BRINGING PEOPLE TOGETHER

DH-IGNITE is a unique event designed to provide Humanities and Social Sciences researchers, students, and practitioners an opportunity to connect with each other, learn from and with each other, and be inspired to try new and innovative research approaches.

2 CHAMPIONS INITIATIVE

EQUIPPING PEOPLE WITH SKILLS & RESOURCES

When completed, the Digital Champions Initiative will offer nine different tracks with various activities for individuals at all skill levels to learn from and contribute. To effectively grow a CoP, the community needs to include not only novices but also those who are more experienced and can act as role models, mentors and trainers.

3 STAKEHOLDER MAP

CREATING AWARENESS OF PEOPLE, OPPORTUNITIES & RESOURCES

Knowing who is interested and involved in digital humanities and computational social sciences activities and what resources and opportunities are available is critical to the success of the CoP. The stakeholder map can help find collaborators, supervisors, students, and resources.

Creating a welcoming learning environment

Through DH-IGNITE, we created opportunities for researchers, students and practitioners to learn about each others' work, ideas, challenges, and solutions. The interactive programme included sessions on research infrastructure, data, learning opportunities, regional DH projects, interdisciplinary collaboration, and even chatGPT.

Connect

Over 200 researchers, students, and librarians from Kwa-Zulu Natal and the Western Cape have participated virtually or in person in DH-IGNITE events in these regions.

Learn

More than 50 presenters from 22 institutions presented talks, lightning talks, panel discussions, and workshops

Grow

"Attending DH-IGNITE [...] has been a valuable opportunity to acquire new knowledge, network with colleagues, and discover innovative tools and methods to enhance my work."

Nokuthula Ndlovu (CPUT)

<https://dh-ignite.org/10.5281/zenodo.7820678>

Opportunities for all

When completed, the Digital Champions Initiative will provide entry points to the programme for people at all skill levels. Participants can move through the different tracks as their experiences and needs change.

Explorer

An introduction to Digital Humanities concepts and projects

Embarker

Start using digital and computational approaches across the research lifecycle

Enhancer

Develop more advanced skills and apply it in your research

Enabler

Discover resources that can facilitate the development of a local community of practice

Educator

Master skills in developing contextualised open educational resources

Empower

Join a community of women using digital and computational skills

Executive

For faculties and departments interested in developing curricula to train staff and students

Exchanger

Meet scholars from all fields, learn to collaborate and understand each other's skills

Engager

For citizens and high school learners to learn about DH

Enhancing visibility of our community and resources

The Stakeholder Map is an interactive platform aimed at collecting and disseminating information about the digital humanities and computational social sciences community and resources in South Africa.

An open, reproducible workflow

Data is collected via a Google Form. Then, an automated workflow developed in R with GitHub actions manipulates the data and creates an interactive visualisation via R Shiny Apps embedded on the ESCALATOR website.

Interactive visualisations

An interactive map shows the general location of projects, people, and training opportunities. Users can zoom in, hover over, and click on individual elements for more information.

Additional data is available in tabular format, including descriptions, keywords, methods, contact details and more.

Who is in the community?

~1,200 people from more than 60 organisations registered for over 200 opportunities

Who did we reach?

The primary target audience for ESCALATOR is the 26 public universities in South Africa. More than 900 from 24 of these institutions were interested in joining our range of activities.

*** Estimated data across all activities offered by ESCALATOR*

What experience do they have with digital/computational research?

**Data from survey of Empower track participants*
[10.5281/zenodo.7820678](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7820678)

Next steps

We are grateful to our community and collaborators for the feedback and input provided since the inception of ESCALATOR!

Over the past 28 months, the ESCALATOR team has learned valuable lessons through engagement with the community. We will continue to roll out successful initiatives such as DH-IGNITE and use the feedback to improve the programme.

01 —————

Refine and enhance communication

We have added qualified communication staff to the ESCALATOR team to help us communicate more efficiently within our community and about the programme.

02 —————

Strengthen partnerships

Building strong relationships with academic faculties and departments, existing and emerging projects, and relevant organisations is critical for success.

03 —————

Improve the value proposition

We are constantly exploring ways to provide better support, more relevant opportunities, and clearer value propositions to encourage active participation in the community.

Acknowledgements

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The programme is developed in collaboration with [Talarify](#).

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We thank you for your continued support in our efforts to help grow an inclusive and active community of practice in Digital Humanities and Computational Social Sciences in South Africa!

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